

Optimal Trajectory Planning with Safety Constraints

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Abstract—The rise of collaborative robotics has offered new opportunities for integrating automation into the factories, allowing robots and humans to work side-by-side. However, this close physical coexistence inevitably brings new constraints for ensuring safe human-robot cooperation. During our research, we developed a trajectory planning algorithm to produce minimum-time yet safe motion plans along specified paths in shared workspaces with humans. To this end, a safety module was used to evaluate the safety of a time-optimal trajectory iteratively. A safe replanning module was developed to optimally adapt the generated trajectory online whenever the optimal plan violates dynamically provided safety limits.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent years have seen an increased interest and effort in developing robotic automation solutions for new market areas, driving technology in the direction of scalable and flexible collaborative robots, mostly working in shared environments alongside humans. However, one of the key elements hindering full exploitation of these collaborative solutions is the difficulty of integrating human safety requirements with classical production constraints, e.g., high-speed operations, fast cycle time capabilities, and path constraints [1].

Typically, production constraints are addressed by planning path-constrained, time-optimal motions [2]. These solutions cannot guarantee safety if the robot has to coexist with humans in unstructured, shared environments. Human safety requirements led to the development of two main paradigms [3]: Speed and Separation Monitoring (SSM) [4], and Power and Force Limiting (PFL) [5].

In the SSM, the relative distance and velocity between the human and the robot are the main factors influencing the robot speed limit, which should guarantee a feasible complete stop before an impact can occur. On the other side, the PFL allows non-zero velocity contacts between the robot and the operator, as long as the energy transferred by the impact is below a certain safety threshold. From the performance point of view, the SSM paradigm may cause the robot to move unnecessarily slow or even stay still when it drives closer to the human worker, thus compromising productivity. Nevertheless, it allows the robot to move at full speed for high separating distances. In contrast, since it does not consider the human-robot separating distance, PFL could reduce the performance when the human is far away from the robot or the robot moves away from the operator [6].

This work was supported in part by the European Unions Horizon 2020 research and innovation program as part of the projects ILIAD (Grant no.732737), and in part by the Italian Ministry of Education and Research in the framework of the CrossLab project (Departments of Excellence).

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Fig. 1. Block diagram of the proposed optimal trajectory planning framework.

In this work we present the trajectory planning algorithm developed in [7] that, combining the two approaches, is able to generate safe trajectories without compromising productivity. The proposed formulation: i) is based on a general framework, applicable to generic paths, robots, and human trajectories; ii) adapts the temporal profile using a convex optimization algorithm, considering the whole dynamics of the robot and limits on the joints velocities, accelerations, and jerk; iii) includes biomechanics injury database and the actual robot’s inertial properties into planning, not relying on conservative and simplified assumptions on robot motion and geometries; iv) dynamically evaluates and enforces online the safety constraints.

II. PROPOSED SOLUTION

We developed an optimization-based trajectory planning framework implemented in an iterative fashion to account for dynamic safety constraints generated online based on information on the human presence and motion provided by a perception system. The solution is based on the iterative planning scheme described in Fig. 1.

Given the desired path to be followed by the robot, first, an initial time-optimal trajectory, considering only the robot actuation limits and possible task-related constraints is generated. The trajectory is obtained using a convex formulation for the path-constrained minimum-time trajectory planning problem, where the non-convex jerk constraints [2] are substituted by a convex upper-bound. After that, the safety of the generated time-optimal trajectory is assessed online by a *Safety Evaluation* module that, based on the robot planned trajectory and the human data from a visual perception system, provides speed constraints for given point of interests (POIs) along the robot structure.

Fig. 2. Examples of trajectories and human motions.

At each time step, the safety module receives the next joint positions and velocities of the trajectory within a horizon h . Then, it acquires information on the human presence from the perception system. If no human is detected, the trajectory over the horizon is labelled as SAFE. If a person is detected, instead, it computes the maximum safe speed v_{max} for each trajectory point over the monitoring horizon and for each robot POI contained into the POI list $\{\text{POI}\}$. This speed is computed by the safe motion unit (SMU), a unified safety framework that relies on biomechanical injury information to ensure the human coworker safety in case of collision [8]–[10].

These safe values are then compared with the actual POI speed and, if for at least one robot POI and at least one trajectory point the safe value is below the actual speed, the planned trajectory is labelled as not safe, and sent to the **Safe Replanning** module for generating a new plan compliant with the new safety limits.

The new optimal trajectory compliant with the safety limits, the robot actuation capabilities, and the task-related constraints is generated using solving again convex jerk-limited optimization algorithm. Once the new plan has been obtained, the next point of the trajectory q_S^* is sent to the robot and the monitoring window is shifted ahead to the next point. However, before providing the **Safety Evaluation** module the next horizon, a **Performance Recovery** procedure is performed to compute a new optimal trajectory that does not consider safety speed constraints. The aim of this recovery procedure is to give to the **Safety Evaluation** module the fastest dynamically consistent trajectory at every cycle. Therefore, we are able to restore high-speed motions as soon as the safety issue that triggered the safe replanning has been resolved, or to evaluate the safety limits over the fastest dynamically possible trajectory.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

We tested our method using two different manipulators, a Franka Emika Panda arm and a Universal Robot UR10e manipulator. Figure 2 shows examples of the trajectories and human motions recorded during the experiments. We considered one robot POI at the end of the last link and safety curves related to collision outcomes with the human chest. The human perception, based on OpenPose, runs at 15 Hz and the planning loop runs at 40 Hz with a monitoring horizon of 25 ms. The safety threshold is set to 1 m. The following table summarizes the results, reporting the percentage of completed tests, the average and the standard deviation of the human-POI distance, and the average velocity of the POI along the impact direction (only positive values):

Completed	\bar{d}_{HPOI}	$\sigma_{d_{\text{HPOI}}}$	\bar{v}_{imp}
100%	1.12 m	0.38 m	0.47 m/s

Fig. 3. Impact velocities and human-POI distances.

Figure 3 shows the impact velocities and the relative human-POI distances. Our approach allows reducing the POI speed when the relative distance is less than the safety threshold and the robot is approaching the human (red area in Fig.3). In all other cases, instead, higher speeds are allowed since they are not a concern for safety.

IV. CONCLUSION

Collaborative robotics has enabled robots to operate in human occupied workspaces without safety cages, bringing new challenges for developing safe yet productive motion planning strategies. The challenge is integrating human safety constraints without compromising the robotic performance goals, which require minimization of the task execution time alongside ensuring its accomplishment. In this work, we presented a trajectory planning algorithm to plan fast and safe motions for collaborative robots in shared environments. The algorithm is based on an iterative procedure that can ensure the nearby human safety by replanning online the time evolution of the motion along the path based on the human data.

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